

**DEONTOLOGICAL CULTURE IN FUTURE
EDUCATORS****Omonova Mukhlisa Dostnazar kizi**

Alfraganus University,

Acting Associate Professor of the Department of "Pedagogy",

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

omonovamuxlisa15@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17484927>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 27st October 2025Accepted: 28th October 2025Online: 29th October 2025**KEYWORDS***Deontology covers not only the
problem of professional duty***ABSTRACT***Each person must fulfill his duty to society, but society
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Each person must fulfill his duty to society, but society must also fulfill its responsibility to citizens. The imbalance between the social duty of a person and the obligations of society to a person can lead to social deviations, which can lead to a reorganization of the structure of humanity.

Deontology covers not only the problem of professional duty, but also issues such as the formation of empathetic relationships in the process of carrying out professional activities, measures and forms of professional responsibility of an employee, maintaining professional secrecy, and methods of overcoming stressful situations.

The determination of the subject, laws, factors of emergence, goals and functions of pedagogical deontology confirms its status as an independent scientific field. A number of scientific studies show that the moral and philosophical basis of pedagogical deontology is the evolution of ideas about the connection between material and spiritual values in society, the need for their development and transmission from generation to generation.

In modern research, pedagogical deontology is being enriched in the following areas:

- the content of organizing professional training of future teachers and preparing them for deontological activities (M.P. Vasilieva and others);
- deontological requirements in the formation of empathetic relationships (M.N. Ermolenko and others);
- the formation of deontological culture and empathetic relationships in teachers (V.M. Grebennikova and others).

As a result of the analysis of special literature and sources, the main functions of the formation of empathetic relationships were identified and classified:

1. Regulatory function - normalizing the behavior of a specialist in various situations arising during his professional activity, clarifying the goals of professional communication,

determining the procedure for making management decisions, and indicating in advance types of unacceptable behavior.

2. Image function - serves to form a positive professional image and collective opinion, strengthen an atmosphere of trust in society.

3. Translational function - allows you to promote cultural values specific to an organization or profession not only among internal employees, but also among the general public.

In our opinion, professional norms serve as an effective tool for the social and professional integration of a person, ensuring the successful socialization and professionalization of his personality. In the empathic relations of representatives of socionomic professions, the normative content is determined mainly by the presence of professional values and the degree of formation of professionally significant qualities.

Ethical norms reflect certain generally accepted categories of human experience, existing social ideals. In order for a person to accept these norms and achieve the level of their application in his activities, he needs to study them, understand their content and form an internal motivational system based on them.

According to our research, along with ethical norms, legal norms and rules of conduct also have a strong influence on the norms of professional behavior. These, in turn, are rules arising from high-level moral norms, and each employee must act on their basis during his work. Such legal requirements are clearly defined in the relevant regulatory and legal documents and job descriptions.

When studying the relationship and interaction of moral and legal norms with behavioral norms in human professional activity, that is, their role as external and internal regulatory mechanisms, the following main components of the deontological training structure were identified: "normative-personal component - a factor that forms an internal moral position; normative-legal component - a system of external normative obligations".

Thus, our terminological analysis shows that: "a professional ideal is the highest behavioral model that a person should strive for in his professional activity, it is considered a level of perfection; a norm is the lower limit of professional behavior, below which it is absolutely unacceptable to fall; norms are reflected in codes of professional conduct".

Thus, the above considerations, analyses, teachings, and definitions form the theoretical basis of our research work. The methodological foundations of the research should be clarified, based on theoretical analyses of the role of deontology in pedagogy, as well as the formation of empathic relationships in the deontological training of future teachers..

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